

THERMOMECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF VARTM-ABLE POSS MODIFIED ROOM-TEMPERATURE EPOXY

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SUMMARY

POSS nano-reinforcements in epoxy matrices have been dispersed and stabilized within room-temperature cure VARTMable epoxy matrices. Mechanical testing demonstrates POSS modified resins have superior thermomechanical properties compared to conventional networks and show very high rubbery plateau modulus and heat distortion.

Keywords: VARTM, epoxy, matrix, nanocomposite, POSS

INTRODUCTION

The marine industry has evolved over the last half decade with the implementation of numerous polymer matrix and fiber-reinforcement structures being manufactured through a variety of composite fabrication techniques. Marine composite matrix resins are generally cured at room-temperature since structures are often too large to economically cure in an oven or autoclave. Isophthalic polyester and vinyl ester matrix resins have dominated the marine industry since they have excellent mechanical properties and curing kinetics optimized for open-mold and large structure laminations. Limitations for polyester matrix composites are primarily associated with long-term stability at the fiber and matrix interface which has been known to degrade over long periods of moisture exposure through ester hydrolysis of the polyester matrices.¹ For smaller pleasure craft and fishing boats, this long-term degradation process is not significant when considering life-cycle economics; however, for larger ships and military vessels, the levels of degradations and uncertainties associated with polyester matrix resins concerns marine architects and engineers. As a result, the development of matrix resins with more stable long-term hydrolytic stability is necessary for broad proliferation of composites into large marine vessels.

When considering a composite matrix hydrolytic stability, shrinkage, fracture toughness, mechanical properties, thermal properties, and fiber-matrix interfacial stability, epoxy resins are generally superior to polyesters. However, high-performance epoxies normally require elevated temperature curing to drive vitrification and polymerization reactions to full conversion and realize ultimate mechanical properties for the material. In addition, epoxy systems are often higher in viscosity than traditional marine laminating resins which limit their utility in marine composite fabrication processes such as vacuum assist resin transfer molding (VARTM). Low-viscosity epoxy resins which cure at room temperature are available, but these systems are designed to

rapidly cure so kinetic generated heat enhances the extent of cure, but these systems tend to gel too quickly for use in marine applications as pot-life is significantly reduced.

We are evaluating room temperature cure POSS modified epoxy resins designed to cure at room temperature which display kinetic and thermomechanical properties that exceed Derakane 510A-40 in mechanical performance. Modification of epoxy polymers with polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxane (POSS) nano-reinforcements has shown to increase thermomechanical properties by incorporating an inorganic structural component to the materials, and allow us to optimize reaction kinetics.^{2,3}

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Derakane 510A-40, EPON 862, diethylenetriamine (DETA), methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (MEKP) Luperox DHD-9 (9% active oxygen solution of MEKP and a plasticizer), 6% cobalt naphthenate, various glass fiber woven rovings (U.S. Composites) and EP409 octaglycidyl POSS (Hybrid Plastics) were used as received.

Vinyl ester matrix preparation

The vinyl ester matrix resins used to fabricate 3-ply and 6-ply VARTM panels were prepared in 300g and 600g batches, respectively. For the vinyl ester laminates, 0.2% cobalt naphthenate (6% active cobalt) was mixed into Derakane resin in an aluminum container using a tongue depressor and stirred for approximately 5 minutes. The initiator, MEKP, was then added at a level of 3:1 MEKP:cobalt naphthenate and mixed for an additional 3-5 minutes until a homogenous mixture was observed. All vinyl ester matrices were immediately introduced into the VARTM fabrication process upon initiation.

Epoxy matrix preparation

The epoxy matrix resins used to fabricate 3-ply and 6-ply VARTM panels were prepared in 300g and 600g batches, respectively. A typical formulation for a 600g 30% POSS modified epoxy matrix was as follows. To a dry aluminum container was charged 372g of EPON 862 and 159g of POSS EP409 (30wt% samples in this manuscript represent wt% of the total epoxy containing monomer). For batches containing POSS, EPON 862 and EP409 were thoroughly mixed for 5 minutes in an aluminum container using a tongue depressor. 69g of DETA was then weighed into the epoxy and vigorously mixed for approximately 5 minutes providing a homogenous mixture. All epoxy matrix resins were prepared at a 1:1 oxirane:amine stoichiometry and immediately incorporated into the VARTM fabrication process upon initiation.

Vacuum Assist Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM)

Composite panels were prepared using a vacuum assist resin transfer molding (VARTM) fabrication procedure. Fiber lay-up packages were composed of three or six plies of 18oz. woven e-glass fiber rovings. These glass woven rovings were placed on a freshly waxed flat aluminum tool. Nylon peel ply and a distribution medium were placed on top of the glass fiber as depicted in Figure 1. Two spiral cut, $\frac{3}{4}$ in., polyethylene tubes were placed the sides of the glass fiber layers for resin inlet and outlet channels. A nylon vacuum bag was then placed over the set-up and secured with high tack sealant tape with extra care to ensure a good seal around the inlet and outlet resin tubes. Vacuum was controlled using an air aspirator connected to the resin outlet tube. Resin formulations were mixed and pulled into the fiber lay-up packages through the resin inlet tube of the VARTM apparatus. All composite panels were cured at ambient conditions for 24h prior to removal from the VARTM process, and then allowed to cure an additional 6 days prior to testing.

Figure 1: VARTM schematic

Analysis

Three-point bending Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) was performed using a TA RSA III. Samples were cut from 3-ply composite panels and tested from 25 – 160°C at a ramp rate of 2°C/min. Heat Distortion Temperature (HDT) analysis was performed on a Rheometric Scientific DMTA V. Samples were analyzed from -80 to 200°C at a ramp rate of 5°C/min. A Materials Testing Systems (MTS) 810 servo-hydraulic test frame was used to analyze the flexural properties for all materials. 6-ply composite panels were into appropriate coupon sized and flex tests were performed using a 1/4 inch round tup three point bend apparatus at a testing speed of 4 mm/min. Samples were 12.7mm in width and 1.7mm thick; a span of 28mm was used for all flexural tests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Derakane 510A-40 is a common room temperature cure vinyl ester matrix resin in the marine industry, and was used in our experimentation as a benchmark resin for comparing room-temperature cured epoxy composite thermomechanical properties. The epoxy resin we selected for our study was EPON 862, which is a commercially

available bisphenol-F based monomer. We diluted the EPON with varying levels of octaglycidyl POSS EP409 and cured the epoxy networks with a stoichiometric equivalent of DETA as shown in Figure 2. We are reviewing four standard matrix formulations which we prepared for this communication:

- 1) Benchmark Derakane 510A-40 cured with MEKP/cobalt naphthenate;
- 2) Epoxy Control, EPON 862 and DETA;
- 3) 30wt% EP409, EPON 862 and DETA;
- 4) 70wt% EP409, EPON 862 and DETA.

Figure 2: Typical room-temperature cure epoxy formulation

Epoxyes were formulated using stoichiometric equivalents of epoxide and amine functionalities with epoxy functionality based upon stoichiometric equivalents of EPON 862 and POSS. Each of the resin formulations showed excellent VARTM processing capability. The resins easily flowed and fully encapsulated various fiber packages, displayed excellent pot-life gel-times that exceeded several hours and demonstrated excellent cure kinetics verified by cured panels being removed easily from the tooling after 24h and which were non-tacky and easy to handle. Figure 3 depicts the VARTM lamination process which consisted of 1 gallon mix tanks used for resin reservoirs. 3-ply laminates and 6-ply laminates were fabricated into 2' x 2' panels. The laminates were effectively free of observable voids in all the panels and displayed excellent behavior when considering flow and resin-fiber wetting. Fully cured laminates also displayed excellent cutting characteristics and machined very well without “fuzzy edges” which we attribute as an excellent indicator of wet-out and cure.

Figure 3: (left) the VARTM process; (right) POSS epoxy matrix composites

DMA was performed on composite samples; representative analyses of the four resin matrices are depicted in Figure 4 and show some very interesting results. The Derakane 510A-40 vinyl ester showed the highest T_g of 102°C which was $10\text{-}20^\circ\text{C}$ above the unmodified and POSS modified epoxy matrix composites. Glass-transition temperature for room-temperature cured epoxy matrices is often considered to be an important hurdle when matching physical properties of room temperature cured epoxies to vinyl ester matrices. Our results show a T_g for the room temperature cure epoxy system to be around 80°C which is consistent with historical values accepted for these resin systems.

We believe storage modulus is a better indicator of matrix performance and utility composites than T_g , and would like to highlight the storage modulus data, indicated by E' , for the epoxy samples above the T_g . When considering modulus at the T_g of vinyl ester, the POSS modified epoxies and the vinyl ester matrix composite moduli are essentially the same at around 3.7 GPa. As temperature continues to increase, the modulus of vinyl ester matrix composites quickly diminish while the POSS modified epoxy matrix composites remain essentially unchanged. This result is significant for indicating the physical characteristics of the composites at elevated temperatures and the POSS modified epoxies clearly have higher thermomechanical properties than the vinyl ester matrix composites. The DMA data for all four composite samples and relevant data is summarized in Table 1. It is important to re-state that the POSS epoxy samples maintain higher modulus across the temperature range even though the Derakane 510A-40 has a higher T_g and thermomechanical properties, we believe, are more important indicators of the capabilities of the materials and independent of T_g .

Figure 4: DMA results of composite samples

Table 1: DMA Moduli and Tg for composite samples

Sample	Tg	E' at RT	E' at 100°C	E' at 150°C
	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	GPa	GPa	GPa
Derakane 510A-40	102	9.3	3.7	0.8
Epoxy Control	83	11.1	1.6	2.0
30wt% POSS Epoxy	85	12.8	3.7	3.7
70wt% POSS Epoxy	89	8.2	3.8	3.9

The differences in thermomechanical performance of the POSS-modified room-temperature cured epoxies compared to conventional vinyl ester matrix composites is further exemplified using HDT testing. The POSS-epoxy composites showed a significant advantage in heat distortion at a constant load as depicted in Figure 5. The unmodified epoxy control and Derakane 510A-40 vinyl ester benchmark composites displayed significant heat distortion in the T_g region at a constant force of 1.8 MPa. The control epoxy displaced 0.20mm, and the vinyl ester was displaced 0.15mm. The samples were 1.7mm thick meaning the epoxy control distorted 12% and the Derakane 510A-40 distorted 9%. The HDT displacement for the 30wt% POSS sample was 0.05mm or 3%, 1/3 that of the Derakane 510A-40 and 1/4 of control epoxy. The 70wt% POSS sample had an even higher stability showing no observable heat distortion in the temperature range reported.

Figure 5: HDT results of composite samples

Table 2 provides a detailed comparison of Derakane 510A vinyl ester, epoxy control, 30wt% POSS epoxy, and 70wt% POSS epoxy and includes information regarding viscosity, pot-life and anticipated shelf-life of the various matrix formulations. In addition, we depict flexural properties for 6-ply composites fabricated through VARTM processing.

Table 2: Thermomechanical performance of POSS epoxy composites under constant force

	Vinyl Ester Peroxide	Epoxy Control Amine	30wt% POSS Amine	70wt% POSS Amine
Type of Curative	Peroxide	Amine	Amine	Amine
Density (g/ml)	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2
Viscosity (Poise)	4	35	10	15
Pot life (hour)	~2.0	~2.0	~2.0	>2
Shelf life (year)	<0.5	1	1	1
Flexural modulus@ RT (GPa)	9.5 ^a	11 ^a	13 ^a	8 ^{a,b}
Flexural modulus@ 100°C (GPa)	3.5 ^a	1.6 ^a	3.7 ^a	3.7 ^{a,b}

a: under current VARTM condition; left out in the wet weather for 7 days

b: lower modulus partly due to slower curing rate of POSS

An MTS was used to evaluate mechanical capabilities of the composite samples, and we employed a three point bending flexural test at room temperature. Figure 6 shows the 3-point bending results and highlights how the epoxy samples outperformed the benchmark Derakane 510A-40 in all aspects of the test: modulus, peak load, strain at peak load, and energy to break (a measure of toughness). It is important to highlight through the flexural testing that we did not see any dramatic loss in mechanical property for the 30% POSS sample as compared to the control epoxy, but able to significantly improve the thermal performance of this matrix as discussed above. We believe the combination of properties highlighted for this formulation are worthy of continued consideration as matrix materials.

Figure 6: 3-Point flex test results of composite samples

Figure 6 shows stress vs. strain curves for the composite panels. The tests were conducted on a MTS servo-hydraulic system with a test speed of 4mm/min. All samples were 1.7 mm thick, 15 mm wide, and had a gauge length of 80 mm. Conditions were determined to provide failure within the gauge. Table 3 shows calculated data from the MTS tensile tests. Notice that the epoxy materials, most notably the control and 30% POSS modified, exhibit a modulus that is much higher than that of Derakane, and they are able to withstand a higher load. The Derakane panels do show greater elongation, however, the enhanced mechanical strength for all epoxy formulations are apparent from this testing.

Figure 6: Composite Stress vs. Strain Curves

Table 3: Composite Stress vs. Strain Calculated Data (3 Samples per Resin)

Sample	Modulus	Peak Load	Strain At Break	Elongation At Break	Energy To Break
	psi	lbf	%	mm	in*lbf
Derakane 510-1	728,476	1,023	6.0	4.8	120
Derakane 510-2	828,284	1,001	5.6	4.5	114
Derakane 510-3	789,090	1,021	5.6	4.5	113
Epoxy Control-1	1,481,877	1,532	4.0	3.2	117
Epoxy Control-2	1,422,033	1,599	4.3	3.4	133
Epoxy Control-3	1,436,101	1,623	4.4	3.5	139
Epoxy with 30% POSS-1	1,273,259	1,610	4.7	3.7	143
Epoxy with 30% POSS-2	1,334,343	1,549	4.3	3.5	129
Epoxy with 30% POSS-3	1,291,560	1,633	4.8	3.8	150
Epoxy with 70% POSS-1	928,676	1,378	5.3	4.2	133
Epoxy with 70% POSS-2	945,213	1,409	5.4	4.3	138
Epoxy with 70% POSS-3	982,896	1,295	4.5	3.6	104

CONCLUSIONS

EP409 octaglycidyl POSS was successfully incorporated into a bisphenol F based epoxy (EPON 862) and cured at room temperature with DETA in a VARTM process to make fiber reinforced composites. The POSS epoxy composites showed significant increases in the thermomechanical properties over the industrial standard vinyl ester formulations as tested in our laboratories. The 30wt% POSS modified epoxy showed an excellent balance in all analysis when considering DMA, heat distortion, and 3-point flexural toughness. These results validate the continued development of POSS modified epoxy formulations for room temperature cure alternative and optimization of POSS levels could show considerable gains in the technology.

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References

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- ¹ Mouritz, A.P; Kootsookos, A., *Comp. Sci. and Tech.*, **2004**, 64, 1503.
 - ² Mather, P.T. et. al. *J. of Poly. Sci.*, **2003**, 41. 24. 3299.
 - ³ Liu, H.; Zheng, S.; Nie, K. *Macromolecules.*, **2005**, 38. 5088.